

Supporting Information

Dynamic Scapping of RTK Domains: Computational Modeling of Natural Products as Dual Modulators of EGFR and VEGFR Signaling in Breast Cancer

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- **Natural Product Library:** The library of ~20,000 natural product compounds was sourced from the Natural Product Database of the University of Johannesburg, Durban University of Technology's natural library, and the MedChemExpress Anticancer Natural Product Library. Structures are available in "natural_products_library.sdf" (SDF Format).
- **Docking Input Files:** Receptor grid files for EGFR (PDB: 1M17) and VEGFR (PDB: 3VHE) are available in "egfr_grid.zip" and "vegfr_grid.zip". Redocked poses (post-DFT optimization) for lead compounds and references are in "docking_poses.zip" (PDB format).
- **Optimized Ligand Geometries:** DFT-optimized geometries (B3LYP/def2-TZVP) of lead compounds and references are provided in "optimized_ligands.zip" (MOL2 format).